

ANALYSIS OF NONLINEAR STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR

OF LAMINATED FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS*

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ABSTRACT

Most composite materials exhibit nonlinear stress-strain behavior; e.g., some unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites have E_2 and G_{12} nonlinearities. The Jones-Nelson-Morgan nonlinear material model is extended to laminates made of these composites. The mechanical properties (Young's moduli, shear moduli, Poisson's ratios) are expressed in terms of the strain energy density of a lamina and the initial slope, curvature, and change of curvature of the respective stress-strain curve. An associated iteration procedure converges to the stress and strain state with secant moduli corresponding to the equivalent linear elastic body. The model is extended to large strain energy values in biaxial stress states by extrapolating the stress-strain curve. Special search and iteration techniques are developed to satisfy the stress-strain relations, stress equilibrium, and strain compatibility throughout the laminate. The model is used to predict experimental load-deflection behavior of boron/epoxy laminates.

INTRODUCTION

The importance of fiber-reinforced composite materials in the aerospace and other industries is well known. These materials are widely used as structural elements because significant weight is saved over conventional metallic structures without sacrificing stiffness or strength. The basic element of laminated fiber-reinforced materials is the lamina in Fig. 1 where the 1-direction is the fiber direction, the 2-direction is transverse to the fibers in the plane of the lamina, and the 3-direction is perpendicular to the plane of the lamina.

Fig. 1 FIBER-REINFORCED LAMINA

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FIG. 2 TYPICAL STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

as shown in Fig. 2. The stress-strain curve in the fiber direction, Fig. 2a, is essentially linear even at high stress levels. However, the stress-strain response transverse to the fibers, Fig. 2b, is often somewhat nonlinear. Finally, the shear response in Fig. 2c is usually quite nonlinear. The degree of the stress-strain curve nonlinearities varies from composite to composite. For example, boron-epoxy and graphite-epoxy have a strong G_{12} nonlinearity but very little E_2 nonlinearity [2]. On the other hand, boron-aluminum has strong E_2 and G_{12} nonlinearities [3]. Moreover, carbon-carbon, a three-dimensionally reinforced composite material, has nonlinearities in all mechanical properties [4]. These nonlinearities generally increase with temperature for all materials and, for epoxy-based composites, with humidity.

The inclusion of some of these stress-strain curve nonlinearities in stress analysis has been attempted before. Petit and Waddoups [5] use an incremental approach to determine the stress-strain response of a lamina and then extend their lamina model to laminates. Alternatively, Hashin, Bagchi, and Rosen [6] use Ramberg-Osgood stress-strain relations to approximate stress-strain curve nonlinearities. In another approach, Hahn and Tsai [7] model the nonlinear shear behavior of boron-epoxy and graphite-epoxy and consider all other stress-strain curves to be linear. Hahn [8] then uses this model in his treatment of nonlinear laminate behavior. In still another approach, Sandhu [9] uses a spline approximation to model the nonlinear shear behavior of boron-epoxy and graphite-epoxy. Jones and Nelson [10-13] develop a nonlinear material model for ATJ-S graphite, a granular composite of low orthotropy. This model has several attractive features such as the capability of treating all stress-strain curve nonlinearities and the inclusion of all multiaxial stress and strain components in the calculation of the mechanical properties of an orthotropic material. Jones and Morgan [14] extend the Jones-Nelson model for ATJ-S graphite to fiber-reinforced composite laminae of high orthotropy but do not treat laminate behavior.

The objective of this paper is to present a procedure for analyzing nonlinear laminate behavior with the Jones-Nelson-Morgan nonlinear material model. This is an essential extension of the Jones-Nelson-Morgan nonlinear lamina model because most structural elements made of fiber-reinforced composite materials are usually laminates instead of laminae. Thus, without this extension, the Jones-Nelson-Morgan model would be severely restricted in its applicability to fiber-reinforced composite materials. Unfortunately, the extension of the nonlinear lamina model to nonlinear laminate behavior is quite complicated.

In nonlinear lamina analysis, the problem is complete when the nonlinear stress-strain relations are satisfied. However, when the laminae are bonded together to form a laminate, they are no longer separate entities and must be analyzed collectively as well as individually. Other conditions must be satisfied in addition to the nonlinear lamina stress-strain relations. In the first part of this paper, these conditions for laminate behavior and the procedure developed for satisfying them are described in detail. This procedure is used to predict the response of symmetric boron-epoxy laminates to uniaxial loads. The predictions are compared to measured load-deflection behavior for boron-epoxy laminates in the second part of the paper.

DERIVATION OF THEORY

The theory for analyzing nonlinear laminate behavior is divided into four parts. The first part is a summary of the Jones-Nelson-Morgan nonlinear lamina model which is used when the layers of the laminate are analyzed individually. Then, the nonlinear laminate load-deflection problem and the conditions which must be satisfied for the laminae to collectively be a laminate are described in the second part. The iteration procedures for satisfying these conditions for laminate load-deflection behavior are presented in the third and fourth parts. In part three, the constant axial strain iteration procedure is developed in which a series of points all with the same axial strain, but not on the laminate load-strain curve, are forced to converge to a point on the laminate load-strain curve. This constant axial strain iteration procedure is a single step in the tangent predictor iteration procedure which is used to find a point on the laminate load-strain curve at a prescribed load from other points on the laminate load-strain curve at lower loads. The tangent predictor method is described in the fourth part of this section.

SUMMARY OF JONES-NELSON-MORGAN NONLINEAR MATERIAL MODEL

In the Jones-Nelson-Morgan model of fiber-reinforced laminae, the mechanical properties of a material, i.e., its Young's moduli, shear moduli, and Poisson's ratios, are expressed in terms of the strain energy density of the stressed and deformed body by use of the relation

$$\text{Mechanical Property}_i = A_i \left[1 - B_i \left(\frac{U}{U_0} \right)^{C_i} \right] \quad (1)$$

where U is the strain energy (density)

$$U = (\sigma_1 \epsilon_1 + \sigma_2 \epsilon_2 + \tau_{12} \gamma_{12}) / 2 \quad (2)$$

and A_i , B_i , and C_i are the slope, curvature, and change of curvature of the stress-strain curve being considered. The quantity U_0 is used to nondimensionalize the strain energy.

The mechanical property - strain energy relation in Eq. (1) must be a good representation of the mechanical property - strain energy data which are merely transformed stress-strain data. In addition, the implied stress-strain relation corresponding to the mechanical property - strain energy relation must be a good approximation of the measured stress-strain data. The degree to which the measured data is approximated is determined by the values of the constants A , B , and C . The constants are most appropriately determined from a least squares error fit of the mechanical property - strain energy data. However, values of the mechanical properties are often needed for strain energies greater than the largest measured strain energy. Thus, the mechanical property - strain energy data (or the stress-strain data) must be extrapolated for large values of strain energy. In the Jones-Nelson-Morgan model for fiber-reinforced materials, the stress-strain data is extrapolated linearly as shown with the dashed line in Fig. 3. The stress-strain curve can be extended linearly in two ways, but, in both extrapolations, the measured data (boxes in Fig. 3) are approximated with

the implied stress-strain relation (solid line in Fig. 3). In one extrapolation, the linear extension is added to the implied stress-strain curve at the last data point. The slope of this linear extension is taken to be the slope of the implied stress-strain curve at the last data point. Alternatively, the implied stress-strain curve can be used past the last data point to a point at which the slope of the curve has a prescribed value. Then, at this point of prescribed slope, the linear extension with slope equal to the prescribed value is used in place of the implied stress-strain curve. A typical mechanical property - strain energy curve which corresponds to the stress-strain curve extrapolation is shown in Fig. 4. Clearly, the mechanical property is never zero but approaches the value of the slope of the linear portion of the stress-strain curve as the strain energy increases. These extrapolations are discussed by Jones and Morgan [14].

In nonlinear lamina analysis, the stresses, strains, and mechanical properties are interdependent. Thus, in the Jones-Nelson-Morgan nonlinear material model, a lamina iteration procedure shown in flowchart form in Fig. 7 of Ref. 10 is used to determine the correct combination of stresses, strains, and mechanical properties for the loads applied to the lamina. At each iteration in this procedure, a linear elastic system with mechanical properties determined from the strain energy of the preceding iteration is analyzed. Elastic mechanical properties are used to start the procedure. At convergence, the final linear elastic system is equivalent to the secant moduli of the nonlinear elastic

FIG. 3 JONES-NELSON-MORGAN EXTRAPOLATED STRESS-STRAIN CURVE

FIG. 4 EXTRAPOLATION OF MECHANICAL PROPERTY BEHAVIOR

system. The lamina iteration technique is the same irrespective of the number of stress-strain curve nonlinearities or the number of loadings. This lamina iteration procedure is used to determine the individual laminae stress-strain states in the laminate analysis procedure.

THE NONLINEAR LAMINATE LOAD-DEFLECTION PROBLEM

In the analysis of a laminate, the individual laminae are the building blocks. If one or more layers of a laminate have nonlinear stress-strain behavior, then the laminate load-strain behavior is also nonlinear as for in-plane loading in Fig. 5. The problem there is to find the strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ corre-

sponding to the applied load \bar{N} with the Jones-Nelson-Morgan nonlinear material model. Laminate load-deflection behavior is usually considered instead of laminate load-strain behavior, but, for this analysis, load-strain behavior is more easily analyzed. Laminate deflections are obtained by integration of the laminate strains; for symmetric laminates under in-plane loading, this integration simply reduces to multiplication of the strains by the appropriate dimensions of the laminate because the laminate stress-strain state is uniform. Thus, the deflection Δ and the strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ are proportional for symmetric laminates under in-plane loading. As a result, the strain axis in Fig. 5 is labeled Δ in parenthesis to indicate the one-to-one relationship between laminate load-strain behavior and laminate load-deflection behavior.

These laminate load-strain problems are solved only for symmetric laminates, i.e., laminates with laminae of the same material, same thickness, and same fiber orientation located in the same position above and below the middle surface of the laminate. Symmetric laminates exhibit pure load-strain behavior under in-plane loading because of lack of coupling between bending and extension. In-plane loading applied to other laminates (antisymmetric and unsymmetric laminates) leads to both extensional and bending deformations because of the presence of coupling stiffnesses. Thus, the strains for antisymmetric and unsymmetric laminates under in-plane loading vary linearly through the thickness of the laminate. The present lamina and laminate analyses cannot be used to obtain the stresses in a laminate with a nonuniform strain state. Hence, antisymmetric and unsymmetric laminate load-strain behavior cannot be analyzed.

The equations used to describe a symmetric laminate under uniaxial loading as shown in Fig. 5 are the conventional load-strain relations of a laminate (the coupling stiffnesses for symmetric laminates are zero):

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{N} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where the A_{ij} are the laminate extensional stiffnesses. The strains ϵ_x^0 , ϵ_y^0 , and γ_{xy}^0 are the middle surface strains. The symmetric laminate does not bend under in-plane loads, so the strains do not vary through the thickness of the laminate. Thus, the strain in each layer of the laminate are the same as the middle surface strains, i.e.,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x(z) \\ \epsilon_y(z) \\ \gamma_{xy}(z) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x^0 \\ \epsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}_k \quad (4)$$

where z is the distance from the middle surface of the laminate in the direction normal to the plane of the laminate, and k is used to denote the k^{th} layer of the laminate. The load-strain relations in Eq. (3) can be inverted so that the strains are expressed in terms of the applied load:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= A_{11}' \bar{N} \\ \epsilon_y &= A_{12}' \bar{N} \\ \gamma_{xy} &= A_{16}' \bar{N} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The A_{ij}' in Eq. (5) are elements of the inverted extensional stiffness matrix when

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11}' &= (A_{22}A_{66} - A_{26}^2)/A \\ A_{12}' &= (A_{16}A_{26} - A_{12}A_{66})/A \\ A_{16}' &= (A_{12}A_{26} - A_{16}A_{22})/A \\ A &= (A_{11}A_{22} - A_{12}^2)A_{66} + 2A_{12}A_{16}A_{26} - A_{11}A_{26}^2 - A_{22}A_{16}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The extensional stiffnesses A_{ij} depend on the mechanical properties which for nonlinear stress-strain behavior depend on the stresses and strains in each layer of the laminate. The strains are constant through the thickness of the laminate, but the stresses in layer k and layer $k+1$ are not the same. Adjacent layers of a laminate have different mechanical properties due to different fiber orientations relative to the laminate coordinate system. Thus, the layer stresses exist because the presence of only σ_{xk} and σ_{xk+1} would lead to different amounts of Poisson and shear deformation in adjoining layers. Thus, each layer of the laminate is in a state of biaxial plane stress. Each lamina must be analyzed individually for these biaxial stress states. However, at the same time, the laminae are bonded together and cannot be treated as separate entities. Thus, three conditions must be satisfied for the collection of laminae to be a symmetric laminate under uniaxial load:

- (1) The strains must be constant through the thickness of the laminate, i.e., the strain state must be the same in each layer of the laminate.
- (2) The stress-strain relations and the mechanical property - strain energy relations must be satisfied simultaneously in each layer of the laminate.
- (3) The layer stresses obtained in condition 2 must be such that the laminate remains in equilibrium; i.e., the resultant forces must be equal to the applied loads.

These three conditions are not easily satisfied for a laminate with laminae that exhibit nonlinear stress-strain behavior. For example, the linear elastic mechanical properties can be used to predict a strain state for an applied load \bar{N} . However, the point in load-strain space, point A in Fig. 6, which corresponds to this applied load and strain state does not lie on the laminate load-strain curve in Fig. 6 because conditions 2 and 3 above are not satisfied. All three conditions can be satisfied with two laminate iteration procedures. The first

FIG. 6
TANGENT PREDICTOR METHOD
FOR ITERATION ALONG THE
LOAD-STRAIN CURVE TO A
SPECIFIC LOAD

procedure called the constant axial strain iteration procedure is used to move vertically from point A, in Fig. 6 to point 1 on the load-strain curve. In most cases, the strain state found in this constant axial strain iteration procedure corresponds to a load other than the applied load. For example, the load N_1 instead of the load N is associated with point 1 on the load-strain curve in Fig. 6. Thus, a second iteration procedure, the tangent predictor method described by Jones [15] is used to move along the load-strain curve from point 1 to point P in Fig. 6. At each iteration, a point off the load-strain curve is determined, and the constant axial strain iteration procedure is used to find the point on the load-strain curve directly beneath this point off the load-strain curve. Both iteration procedures are described with the constant axial strain iteration procedure discussed first.

CONSTANT AXIAL STRAIN ITERATION PROCEDURE

The first part of the iteration procedure to find the strain state for a specific load \bar{N} is to move vertically at a constant axial strain from a point not on the load-strain curve to a point that is on the load-strain curve. At a point off the load-strain curve, the strain state is such that the resultant forces N_y and N_{xy} are not both zero for the correct combination of layer stresses and mechanical properties. In the constant axial strain procedure, the strain ϵ_x at the point not on the load-strain curve is held fixed, and the strains ϵ_y and γ_{xy} are changed in an orderly manner until the resultants N_y and N_{xy} are both zero. When the strains ϵ_y and γ_{xy} are changed, all the resultant forces, N_x as well as N_y and N_{xy} , change. Thus, many points on the vertical line $\epsilon_x = \epsilon_{x1}$ in Fig. 7 are found during iteration from point A_1 off the load-strain curve to point 1 on the load-strain curve. The steps of the constant axial strain iteration procedure for the orderly adjustments of the strains ϵ_y and γ_{xy} to find a point on the load-strain curve are shown in their logical sequence in Fig. 8.

The initial strain state to be investigated in the constant axial strain iteration procedure in Fig. 8 is calculated for a prescribed load with the mechanical properties at a point previously found to be on the load-strain curve. For example, the linear elastic properties (the properties at the origin of the load-strain curve) are used to find point A_1 in Fig. 7. Accordingly, the tangent mechanical properties at point 1 in Fig. 6 are used to find point A_2 . The layer stress-strain relations and the layer mechanical property - strain energy relations are not satisfied for these strains. As a result, the point defined with the initial strain state examined in the constant axial strain iteration procedure and the corresponding prescribed load is not on the laminate load-strain curve.

FIG. 7 TYPICAL SEQUENCE OF POINTS FOUND IN THE CONSTANT AXIAL STRAIN ITERATION PROCEDURE FOR FINDING A POINT ON THE LOAD-STRAIN CURVE FROM A POINT OFF THE LOAD-STRAIN CURVE

FIG. 8 CONSTANT AXIAL STRAIN ITERATION PROCEDURE TO FIND LOAD AT ϵ_{x1}

The first step in the constant axial strain iteration procedure is to calculate the correct layer stresses and mechanical properties for the strain state under consideration. These layer stresses and mechanical properties are found with the lamina stress analysis iteration procedure described by Jones and Nelson [10]. This lamina iteration procedure is used because the layer stresses, strains, and mechanical properties are interdependent. Each layer is analyzed individually. In addition, the strain state is considered to be the same in each layer so that the laminate strain compatibility condition is always satisfied.

After the stress-strain relations and mechanical property - strain energy relations are satisfied for each layer of the laminate, the resultant forces acting on the laminate are calculated by integrating the layer stresses through the thickness of the laminate. For the load-deflection problem, the stresses are constant in each layer of the laminate so the integration to obtain the resultant forces reduces to summation of the products of the layer stresses and respective layer thicknesses:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_x &= \sum_{k=1}^{NL} \sigma_{xk} t_k \\
 N_y &= \sum_{k=1}^{NL} \sigma_{yk} t_k \\
 N_{xy} &= \sum_{k=1}^{NL} \tau_{xyk} t_k
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{7}$$

where k is the layer number and NL is the total number of layers in the laminate.

The next step in the constant axial strain iteration procedure is to examine laminate force equilibrium. First, the resultant force N_{xy} is considered. If N_{xy} is not zero, the strain state is changed by increasing or decreasing the shear strain enough times until $N_{xy} = 0$. The method for increasing or decreasing the shear strain is discussed in the next paragraph. After γ_{xy} is adjusted until $N_{xy} = 0$, ϵ_y is increased or decreased in a similar manner as many times as necessary to make $N_y = 0$. Each time ϵ_y is changed, N_{xy} also changes. Thus, the iterations on the shear strain to make $N_{xy} = 0$ must be repeated for each change in ϵ_y . The shear iterations γ_{xyij} in Fig. 8 have a double subscript because the shear strain must be increased or decreased more than once for each change in ϵ_y . The subscript j is used to indicate the j^{th} change in the shear strain for the i^{th} change in the transverse strain ϵ_y .

The strain γ_{xy} is changed in the following way. If N_{xy} is positive/negative, γ_{xyij} is too large/small and must be decreased/increased. Then, new mechanical properties and layer stresses must be determined because the laminate strain state (and hence layer strain states) is changed when γ_{xy} is changed. The amount by which γ_{xy} should be increased or decreased is difficult to predict, so an interval halving technique (binary search) is used to find $\gamma_{xy}^{\#}$, the shear strain at which $N_{xy} = 0$. The initial shear strain γ_{xyij} is decreased/increased by the amount $\gamma_{xyij}/4$ if N_{xy} is positive/negative. If N_{xy} is still positive/negative after the γ_{xyij} layer stresses and laminate resultant forces are recalculated, γ_{xyij} is again decreased/increased by $\gamma_{xyij}/4$. The shear strain is decreased/increased by $\gamma_{xyij}/4$ until N_{xy} is negative/positive. Thus, an interval $\gamma_{xyin+1} < \gamma_{xyi} < \gamma_{xyin}$ ($\gamma_{xyin} < \gamma_{xyi} < \gamma_{xyin+1}$) is found in which the shear strain $\gamma_{xy}^{\#}$ is located. This interval around $\gamma_{xy}^{\#}$ is halved until $\gamma_{xy}^{\#}$ is known to the desired level of accuracy. (In a computer program developed for laminate load-strain analysis, γ_{xy} is changed until $N_{xy}/N_x < .001$.)

The strain in the y -direction is altered until $N_y = 0$ in a manner similar to the way in which the shear strain is changed until $N_{xy} = 0$. If N_y is positive/negative, ϵ_{yi} is decreased/increased. (For uniaxial loading in the x -direction, the strain ϵ_y is negative, so an increase/decrease in the absolute value of ϵ_y corresponds to a decrease/increase in the actual value of ϵ_y .) All the laminate resultant forces, as well as the layer stresses and mechanical properties, change for each iteration ϵ_{yi} . Thus, each time ϵ_y is changed, the preceding steps in the constant axial strain iteration procedure in Fig. 8 must be repeated. That is, the correct layer stresses and mechanical properties must be recalculated and the shear strain must be altered many times until $N_{xy} = 0$. Finally, after many iterations on $\epsilon_y^{\#}$ in the interval halving procedure, the strain $\epsilon_y^{\#}$ for which $N_y = 0$ is found. In the determination of $\epsilon_y^{\#}$, the strain $\gamma_{xy}^{\#}$ corresponding to $\epsilon_y^{\#}$ is also found such that both N_y and N_{xy} are zero at the same time. The layer stress-strain relations and mechanical property - strain energy relations are also satisfied. Hence, all the conditions for a point to be on the load-strain

curve are satisfied, so the constant axial strain iteration procedure is stopped.

Each iteration on either γ_{xy} or ϵ_y leads to a point on the vertical line $\epsilon_x = \epsilon_{x1}$ in Fig. 7. The stress-strain relations and the mechanical property - strain energy relations are satisfied at each point on the vertical line except at point A₁. Point A₁ is the initial point not on the load-strain curve. Points B through F correspond to successive iterations on the strain ϵ_y . At points B through F, the resultant N_{xy} is zero. Point l, the point on the load-strain curve, corresponds to the last iteration on ϵ_y and is located between point F at which $N_y > 0$ and point E at which $N_y < 0$. The points b₁, b₂, b₃, and b₄ in Fig. 7 correspond to the iterations on the shear strain needed to make $N_{xy} = 0$ for the strain ϵ_{y1} . The resultant N_{xy} is positive at points b₁ and b₂ below point B and is negative at points b₃ and b₄ above point B. A series of points similar to points b₁, b₂, b₃, and b₄ surround each of the points B, C, D, E, F, and l in Fig. 7.

A large number of points on the vertical line $\epsilon_x = \epsilon_{x1}$ must be calculated before a point on the load-strain curve is found. For example, in order to find point l in Fig. 7, at least five points corresponding to shear strain iterations (points b₁, b₂, b₃, b₄, and point B) must be found for each iteration on ϵ_y . Six iterations on ϵ_y (points B, C, D, E, F, and l) are shown in Fig. 7, but several more iterations on ϵ_y are needed if point l is to be determined accurately. However, the additional points cannot be shown clearly at the scale of Fig. 7. For each iteration on γ_{xy} or ϵ_y , the stresses and mechanical properties for each layer of the laminate must be calculated. Hence, for a three-layer symmetric laminate, the iteration procedure for lamina stress analysis must be performed more than 90 times to find point l in Fig. 7. However, in many laminate load-strain problems more than five shear strain iterations are needed to make $N_{xy} = 0$, and more than six iterations are needed on the strain ϵ_y to make $N_y = 0$. A computer must obviously be used to handle the large number of calculations in the iteration procedure.

More complicated laminate problems in which the applied loads N_y and N_{xy} are prescribed nonzero values \bar{N}_y and \bar{N}_{xy} can also be solved with an iteration procedure similar to the one described in this section. The strains γ_{xy} and ϵ_y are simply changed until $N_{xy} = \bar{N}_{xy}$ and $N_y = \bar{N}_y$.

TANGENT PREDICTOR METHOD

After a point on the load-strain curve is found from a point off the load-strain curve by use of the constant strain iteration procedure, the load associated with the point on the load-strain curve is compared to the prescribed load. If this load is equal to the prescribed load, the desired strain state has been found. If the load is not equal to the prescribed load, the mechanical properties at this point on the load-strain curve are used in the tangent predictor iteration procedure to predict a strain state corresponding to a load closer than the previous load to the prescribed load.

Several points on the load-strain curve found during a typical tangent predictor iteration procedure are shown in Fig. 6. Point l on the load-strain curve is found by use of the linear elastic mechanical properties to calculate the strain state corresponding to the load \bar{N} . The difference between \bar{N} and N_1 , ΔN_1 , is then used in the incremental strain load relations to predict an incremental strain state $\Delta\epsilon_{x1}$, $\Delta\epsilon_{y1}$, and $\Delta\gamma_{xy1}$. The incremental strain-load relations are:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\epsilon_x \\ \Delta\epsilon_y \\ \Delta\gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A}'_{11} & \bar{A}'_{12} & \bar{A}'_{16} \\ \bar{A}'_{21} & \bar{A}'_{22} & \bar{A}'_{26} \\ \bar{A}'_{61} & \bar{A}'_{62} & \bar{A}'_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta N \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where, \bar{A}'_{ij} are elements of the inverted incremental extensional stiffness matrix. The \bar{A}'_{ij} are obtained by a series of variational operations on the mechanical

property - strain energy relations in Eq. (1), on the strain energy expression in Eq. (2), on the individual lamina stress-strain relations, and finally on the laminate load-strain relations in Eq. (3). The derivation of the A_{ij} by Morgan [16] is quite complicated and too long for presentation here.

The strain state at point A_2 in Fig. 6 is found by adding the incremental strain state $\Delta\epsilon_{x1}$, $\Delta\epsilon_{y1}$, $\Delta\gamma_{xy1}$ to the strain state at point 1, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{xA_2} &= \epsilon_{x1} + \Delta\epsilon_{x1} \\ \epsilon_{yA_2} &= \epsilon_{y1} + \Delta\epsilon_{y1} \\ \gamma_{xyA_2} &= \gamma_{xy1} + \Delta\gamma_{xy1}\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

The constant axial strain iteration procedure is then used to determine point 2 on the load-strain curve in Fig. 6 from point A_2 . Points 3 and 4 in Fig. 6 and other points on the load-strain curve closer than points 3 and 4 to point P (points not shown in Fig. 6 for the sake of clarity) are found in the same manner that point 2 is found from point 1.

The sequence of steps in the tangent predictor method is summarized in Fig. 9. First, the strain state for the prescribed load calculated with the linear elastic mechanical properties is used as input to the constant axial strain iteration procedure to find an initial point on the load-strain curve. The difference in load ΔN between the load at this initial point on the load-strain curve and the prescribed load is calculated. Then, an incremental strain state for ΔN is calculated with the incremental stress - incremental strain relations which involve the tangent mechanical properties at the initial point on the load-strain curve. Next, the incremental strain state is added to the strain state at the preceding point on the load-strain curve. Thus, a new strain state for the prescribed load is obtained. The correct strain state for the prescribed load is found when ΔN is negligibly small.

FIG. 9 TANGENT PREDICTOR METHOD TO FIND STRAINS FOR A PRESCRIBED LOAD

NONLINEAR RESPONSE OF SYMMETRIC BORON-EPOXY LAMINATES TO UNIAXIAL LOADING

In order to test the procedure for applying the Jones-Nelson-Morgan nonlinear material model to nonlinear laminate behavior, predicted strains for symmetric boron-epoxy laminates subjected to uniaxial loading are compared to boron-epoxy laminate strains measured by Cole and Pipes [2]. Cole and Pipes present load-strain curves for four symmetric boron-epoxy laminates. The stacking sequences of these laminates are $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$, $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]_S$, $[0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]_S$ and $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$. These stacking sequences are used to indicate the fiber direction of the layers of the laminate relative to the coordinate system in which the laminate is fabricated. However, for the load-strain curves measured by Cole and Pipes, these laminates are not loaded in the same coordinate system as the one used to define the lamination sequences. Instead the laminates are loaded at angles of 15° and 30° relative to the fabrication coordinate system. That is, if the laminate is fabricated in the x-y coordinate system in Fig. 10,

FIG. 10 x-y COORDINATE SYSTEM FOR A LAMINATE

the laminate test specimens are cut out at 15° and 30° to the x-y coordinate system so that when the specimens are loaded in the testing machine, the uniaxial loads are applied at 15° and 30° relative to the x-direction in Fig. 10. Thus, a laminate with a lamination sequence of $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ in the x-y coordinate system in Fig. 10 has a stacking sequence of $[60^\circ/-30^\circ]_{2S}$ in the direction of the load if the test specimen is cut out at 15° relative to the fabrication coordinate system and a stacking sequence of $[75^\circ/-15^\circ]_{2S}$ in the direction of the load if the test specimen is cut out at 30° relative to the fabrication coordinate system.

Strain predictions are presented in this section for the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ boron-epoxy laminate under uniaxial loads applied at 15° and 30° relative to the fabrication coordinate system and for the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ boron-epoxy laminate under uniaxial loads applied at 15° and 30° to the fabrication coordinate system.

The bar over the 90° layer in the stacking sequence of the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate is used to denote that the laminate has a single 90° layer located in the center, i.e., the complete stacking sequence is $[0^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/45^\circ/0^\circ]$. The mechanical property expressions used to make these strain predictions are presented by Jones and Morgan [14]. Strain predictions are obtained for the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]_S$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]_S$ boron-epoxy laminates, but the results are not presented because the differences between the predicted and measured strains are so small that the predicted and measured load-strain curves are almost indistinguishable. Also, both the predicted and measured curves are almost linear so a good evaluation of the nonlinear material model is not obtained from an analysis of these laminates.

The predicted and measured load-strain curves for a $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ laminate with loads applied at 15° to the fabrication coordinate system are shown in Fig. 11. The strains are plotted against the average laminate stresses. The average laminate stress is defined as the load applied to the laminate divided by the total thickness of the laminate. Each layer of the laminates has a thickness of .005 inches, so the total laminate thickness for each laminate depends on the number of layers in the laminate. The $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ laminate has a total thickness of .04 inches. (The $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate has a total thickness of .045 inches because the laminate has a single 90° layer located in the center of the laminate). The predicted axial strains in Fig. 11 are less than the axial strains measured for three laminate test specimens. Likewise, the transverse strain predictions are less in absolute value than the measured transverse strains.

However, if the loads are applied at 30° relative to the fabrication coordinate system for the same $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ laminate, the predicted axial load - axial strain curve falls between the measured axial load - axial strain curves as shown in Fig. 12.

FIG. 11 STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF A $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ BORON-EPOXY LAMINATE; LOADS APPLIED AT $\theta = 15^\circ$

FIG. 12 STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF A $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ BORON-EPOXY LAMINATE; LOADS APPLIED AT $\theta = 30^\circ$

FIG. 13 STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF A $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ BORON-EPOXY LAMINATE; LOADS APPLIED AT $\theta = 15^\circ$

FIG. 14 STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF A $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ BORON-EPOXY LAMINATE; LOADS APPLIED AT $\theta = 30^\circ$

The comparison of the predicted and measured load-strain curves for the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ boron-epoxy laminate is similar to the comparison of the predicted and measured curves for the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ laminate. For loads applied at 15° relative to the fabrication coordinate system, the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate strains in Fig. 13 are less than the three sets of measured strains at all load levels. The predicted load-strain curve in Fig. 14 for the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate subjected to loads applied at 30° to the fabrication coordinate system falls between the three measured load-strain curves. However, unlike the predicted load-strain curves for the $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$ boron-epoxy laminate, the predicted load-strain curves in Figs. 13 and 14 for the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate are almost linear. The linear load-strain curve prediction is not valid for the $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ laminate under 15° off-axis loading because the corresponding measured load-strain curves in Fig. 13 are not linear. On the other hand, the linear load-strain curve prediction in Fig. 14 is valid because the measured load-strain curves are also almost linear.

The predicted strains shown in Figs. 11, 12, 13, and 14 are not always close to the measured strains. However, if the inconsistencies in Cole and Pipes' shear data due to the aging of the material are considered [14], the correlation between the predicted and measured boron-epoxy laminate strains is good enough to say that the present theory nonlinear material model can be used to predict boron-epoxy laminate behavior reasonably well.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A significant extension of the Jones-Nelson-Morgan material model for the nonlinear behavior of fiber-reinforced composite materials is described. In this extension from lamina analysis to laminate analysis, simultaneous conditions of laminate strain compatibility, stress-strain interrelationships, and force equilibrium are satisfied in a multilevel iteration procedure. On the first level, the constant axial strain iteration procedure is used to find a point on the laminate load-strain curve from a point off the load-strain curve through a series of changes in the strains ϵ_y and γ_{xy} . The constant axial strain iteration procedure is a single step in the overall iteration procedure, the tangent predictor method. In the tangent predictor method, the tangent mechanical properties at a point on the laminate load-strain curve are used to find a new point on the load-strain curve which is closer than the original point to the desired point on the load-strain curve. These laminate iteration procedures are applicable to boron-epoxy and graphite-epoxy with their G_{12} nonlinearity, to boron-aluminum with its E_2 and G_{12} nonlinearities, and to carbon-carbon with its nonlinearities in all mechanical properties. Agreement of strains predicted with these iteration procedures with measured boron-epoxy laminate strains is reasonably good. The theory presented here is also important for predicting laminate stiffnesses for other types of problems such as laminate buckling analysis.

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